

The role of composition and preparation method on laser performance of holmium-doped silica fibers

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ABSTRACT

The composition of holmium-doped fibers has a fundamental influence on their fluorescence and laser properties. The same can apply for the preparation method, since it may affect the glass matrix in the close vicinity of active ions. We present fibers with different dopant levels, namely Al₂O₃ and Ho³⁺, prepared through several methods to find their relations to fiber characteristics. We investigated fluorescence lifetime, laser threshold and laser slope efficiency as a function of Al/Ho molar ratio and Al₂O₃ content. It was proved laser slope efficiency is affected primarily by Al/Ho ratio; for high-efficiency fibers with low laser threshold the Al/Ho needs to be greater than 50. Fluorescence lifetime was found to depend on both Al/Ho ratio and on total Al₂O₃ content. It was increasing with Al/Ho ratio as well as with total Al₂O₃ concentration. The best-performing fibers showed slope efficiency above 70%, laser threshold below 200 mW and fluorescence lifetime longer than 1200 μs.

1. Introduction

Holmium-doped fiber lasers (HDFL) based on silica glass are well-established sources for a spectral region beyond 2 μm. Utilization of HDFL has been demonstrated in various applications [1,2] covering medicine, remote sensing or directed-energy systems. For high-power applications, HDFL can be conveniently resonantly pumped at 1950 nm by thulium-doped fiber lasers (TDFL) [3], which offers quantum defect of only about 7%. Although scaling-up the HDFL output power depends primarily on the performance of TDFL and a suitable laser arrangement, increasing the HDFL efficiency is an essential need.

It was already shown that the laser parameters of HDFL strongly depend on fiber composition [4–6]. Aluminum oxide (alumina) is the most widespread co-dopant in active fibers doped with rare earth (RE) ions which is added to prevent unwanted RE clustering and quenching effects. Hence, the laser performance is primarily affected by the Al/Ho molar ratio. For high-performance lasers, the Al/Ho ratio needs to be at least 50. We have recently observed that absolute alumina concentration may also play a role [5]. However, comprehensive study has not yet been performed. Also, the influence of preparation technology on fiber parameters has not yet been investigated in detail. Our work shall fill these gaps.

Active optical fibers are commonly drawn from preforms prepared from ultra-pure precursors utilizing vapor phase deposition technology.

Modified chemical vapor deposition (MCVD) is a method in which deposition occurs under defined conditions in a protected environment at the inner wall of a substrate tube [7] and it is the most widespread technique used for high-purity optical preform preparation. Oxide precursors are volatile reactants that are evaporated from liquid phase and oxidized at high temperatures. To extend the nature of optical dopants and co-dopants, MCVD can be combined with solution doping or nanoparticle doping, where porous silica layer is soaked with doping medium prior vitrification and tube collapsing.

Solution doping is a method in which soluble salts are used to introduce dopants into the preform core [8]. The method was developed in the 1980's and today remains the most widespread technique for preparation of active fibers. In 2007 an analogous technique called nanoparticle doping [9], which uses dispersion of ceramic nanoparticles, has been established. Both methods are easy to handle, straightforward, versatile and widely used for various types of fibers [10–14]. However, the process of soaking a single porous layer limits the core size, and doping outside the controlled environment involves a risk of contamination. Such limitations are overcome in the gas phase doping technology (chelate delivery system), where the dopants are sublimated from a solid phase [15] and multiple repetitions allow to tailor the fiber core diameter or inner structure [16]. On the other hand, the method is costly and makes high demands on equipment, maintenance and operation.

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Much higher yields of vitrified core material, as well as perfectly flat radial concentration and thus step-like refractive index profiles of preforms can be obtained using a powder-based sintering approach, e.g. REPUSIL [17,18]. It involves synthesis of doped silica powder, its compaction, thermal drying and purification and final vitrification. Using this method, the doped core material is free of layered structures and provides a yield of several tens of grams per single batch synthesis.

In this paper, we investigate laser fibers drawn from preforms manufactured using different preparation technologies: (i) MCVD in combination with doping using dispersion of synthesized mixed Al_2O_3 : Ho_2O_3 nanoparticles and (ii) powder-based approach. In addition, we have taken over our previously published data for fibers prepared by (iii) MCVD in combination with solution doping and (iv) MCVD in combination with a dispersion containing commercial Al_2O_3 nanoparticles and dissolved HoCl_3 . Each of the preform manufacturing technologies experiences different chemical reaction pathways and thermal management schemes. This might result in different structures of resulting glass matrix in the vicinity of active ions, which in turn would influence resulting fiber laser performance.

We compare fluorescence lifetimes and laser parameters of various Ho/Al-doped fibers drawn from different preform types. We present a comprehensive study of the influence of preform manufacturing technology and fiber composition on fluorescence lifetime, laser threshold and laser slope efficiency.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparation of preforms

2.1.1. MCVD-derived preforms

Fused silica tubes (F300, Heraeus) with OD/ID 18/15.2 mm were used as substrates. Extra pure SiCl_4 (Siridion STC 100, Evonik) and onsite purified oxygen (dew point $< -99.9^\circ\text{C}$) served as SiO_2 precursors. After an initial fire polishing step and deposition of two buffer SiO_2 layers, a porous silica layer was formed. The porous layer was then soaked with an ethanolic dispersion of Al_2O_3 : Ho_2O_3 co-doped nanoparticles. The doped layer was subsequently dried, sintered (under a chlorine atmosphere) and collapsed into an optical preform.

The Al_2O_3 : Ho_2O_3 co-doped nanoparticles were synthesized through co-precipitation by dropwise addition of an acidic solution containing Al^{3+} ($\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.9995%, Thermo Fischer Scientific) and Ho^{3+} ($\text{HoCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.9%, Sigma Aldrich) into an alkaline solution containing NH_3 , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ and NaOH (all analytic grade) under vigorous stirring. For particle separation, polyvinylpyrrolidone (MW $4 \cdot 10^4$, VWR AMRESCO) at a concentration of 2 wt% based on equivalent Al_2O_3 mass was employed. The molar ratios in the final mixture were $\text{Al}^{3+}:\text{NH}_3:(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4:(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3:\text{NaOH}:\text{H}_2\text{O} = 1:5:1:1:0.01:554$. Holmium concentrations were adjusted to achieve defined Al/Ho ratios. After complete precipitation, the particles were centrifuged and washed with deionized water three times, dried at 90°C , ground in an agate mortar and pre-calcined at 200°C . The nanoparticles were approximately 80 nm in their as-synthesized form. The nanoparticles were dispersed in absolute ethanol (VWR) and intensively ultrasonicated to obtain a stable dispersion.

2.1.2. Powder-derived preforms

A silica suspension was doped using $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.9995%, Thermo Fischer Scientific) and $\text{HoCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.9%, Sigma Aldrich) following a proprietary procedure. Subsequently, the obtained powder was compacted to a cylinder to form a so-called green body. The green body was thermally dried and purified using chlorine atmosphere. Vitrification was done using a glass blower lathe and a F320 tube (Heraeus) for cladding and holding the cylinder during processing.

2.2. Preparation of fibers

All preforms were processed into single-mode fibers. Their outer diameter was $125 \mu\text{m}$ ($\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$) and their core size around $7 \mu\text{m}$. The fibers were protected with a UV-curable high refractive index acrylate coating (Cablelite 3471-3-14, DSM Functional Materials). MCVD-derived preforms were drawn to fibers, without any intermediate steps. Powder-derived preforms were drawn first to rods of $900 \mu\text{m}$ and one rod of each material was then inserted into a F300 tube (Heraeus) OD/ID 30/3 mm elongated to 10.5/1.08 mm. Final fiber manufacturing was done via rod-in-tube technique.

2.3. Preforms characterization

Refractive index profiles (RIPs) of the MCVD-derived preforms were measured along a preform using an A2600 profiler (Photon Kinetics). Concentration profiles of Al_2O_3 were obtained using wavelength dispersive electron probe microanalysis (EPMA) using wavelength-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy utilizing JEOL JXA-8230 and JXA8800L analyzers. In the case of MCVD-derived preforms, polished preform cross-cuttings were analyzed in 20 equidistant points across the core and 10 points from the flat-top maximum around the center were used to calculate the average value. The concentration of Ho^{3+} was calculated from the main absorption peak at 1950 nm measured with a Nicolet 8700 FT-IR spectrometer.

In the case of powder-derived preforms, the radial chemical distribution profiles of Ho, Al and Si of the preform core cross sections were determined using line scans on carbon coated samples at a step size of $50 \mu\text{m}$. The energy of the exciting electrons was set to 25 keV, the beam current was 500 nA and it was defocused to a diameter of $50 \mu\text{m}$. Subsequently, fully quantitative measurements at five selected positions along each line scan were carried out and used to scale the recorded line profiles.

2.4. Fibers characterization

2.4.1. Fluorescence lifetime

Fluorescence lifetimes of the $\text{Ho}^{3+} {}^5\text{I}_7 \rightarrow {}^5\text{I}_8$ transition were determined according to a detection setup where a stripped fiber was excited with various pump powers and emission was detected from the side. The resulting decay curves were normalized and a time value at the $1/e$ point was determined as the decay time for each excitation power. Decay times were extrapolated to the zero-excitation power using equation (1), described in details elsewhere [19], to eliminate the detrimental effect of amplified spontaneous emission and energy transfer effects.

$$\tau = \frac{\tau_0}{1 + \left(\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_{\text{SAT}}} - 1 \right) \cdot \left(\frac{P}{P + P_{\text{CRIT}}} \right)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where τ is the decay time obtained from $1/e$ intensity value on the normalized decay curve, P is excitation power, τ_0 is fluorescence lifetime (decay time extrapolated to zero excitation power), τ_{SAT} is the saturated lifetime (decay time extrapolated to infinite excitation power) and P_{CRIT} is the critical excitation power. The value of τ_0 is thus obtained as parameter of the fit.

2.4.2. Fiber laser setup

A Fabry-Perot laser configuration, depicted schematically in Fig. 1, was used for laser testing. Tested fibers were pumped by a Tm-doped fiber laser, which was pumped by an Er/Yb ring laser (EDFL). The Tm-doped fiber laser consisted of thulium-doped fiber (TDF) and a pair of Bragg gratings (HRFBG and LRFBG at 1950 nm). The maximum output power at 1950 nm was approximately 1 W. The Ho-doped fiber laser cavity was formed by holmium-doped fiber (HDF) under evaluation, highly-reflective fiber Bragg grating (HRFBG) at 2100 nm

Fig. 1. Fiber laser setup.

($R \sim 99.5\%$) and perpendicularly cleaved fiber end ($R \sim 3.5\%$). Tested fibers were gradually shortened to find the optimal fiber length (L_{opt}). For each fiber length, laser threshold and slope efficiency (SE) with respect to the absorbed pump power were determined.

3. Results and discussion

We prepared a total of 8 different HDFs representing various Al/Ho molar ratios in a range roughly 20-75 using the MCVN nanoparticle doping and the powder-based approach. Table 1 summarizes the chemical composition of the fibers and their fluorescence and laser parameters. Fibers denoted NP_Al,Ho were prepared using dispersion of synthesized co-doped nanoparticles and fibers prepared through the powder-based approach are marked as Powder. In general, the background losses ranged from 20 to 40 dB/km.

The measurement of the fluorescence lifetime is shown in Fig. 2 using the example of NP_Al,Ho_1 fiber. The fluorescence decay at low powers exhibited single exponential character as shown in the inset and increasing power caused shortening of the decay and deviations from single exponentiality owing to the presence of energy transfer processes. The fluorescence lifetime extrapolated to zero power was obtained from the decay times using Eq. (1) as depicted in Fig. 2b; the value is nearly identical to the single exponential fit of the low power curve.

For correlations to preform manufacturing technique and composition, the properties of HDFs are plotted as a function of Al/Ho molar ratio; Figs. 3–5 display slope efficiencies, laser thresholds, and fluorescence lifetimes respectively. The error in determining the measured quantities was estimated to be 2 percent and 1 percent point in the case of slope efficiency. We also included data, already published elsewhere [4,5], of fibers prepared by solution doping and nanoparticle doping using commercial Al_2O_3 nanoparticles. Due to observed differences, the taken-over nanoparticle-doped fibers were divided into two categories – lowly doped (up to 4 mol.% of Al_2O_3 , marked NP_low) and highly doped containing around 9 mol.% of Al_2O_3 (denoted NP_high). Note, the solution-doped fibers (SD) were also lowly doped with alumina, i.e. up to 4 mol.% of Al_2O_3 .

We observed two regimes in the plot of SE vs. Al/Ho, cf. Fig. 3. Up to Al/Ho around 50, laser slope efficiency increases linearly before leveling off at higher ratios. Further increase of the Al/Ho leads to only a minor improvement at the expense of increasing numerical aperture requiring reduced core diameter. Also, the SE data points are similar for all manufacturing groups. This indicates that SE is independent of preform preparation method. Therefore, Al/Ho molar ratio is the most important parameter for enabling high slope efficiency and an Al/Ho ratio of at

least 50 provides high-efficiency HDFs.

The laser threshold decreases with increasing Al/Ho ratio, see Fig. 4. This trend is in accordance with slope efficiency. There is a noticeable difference in laser threshold between fibers with low (NP_low and SD) and high (Powder, NP_Al,Ho and NP_high) content of Al_2O_3 . Even though the data are quite scattered, the trend appears to be significant; about one-third value of laser threshold was obtained in the case of high Al_2O_3 doping comparing similar Al/Ho ratios. This difference can be ascribed to the optimal fiber lengths in a laser resonator. For a given Al/Ho ratio, fibers with high-content of Al_2O_3 show higher concentrations of Ho^{3+} , compared to fibers lowly-doped with Al_2O_3 , and thus their optimal fiber lengths are shorter. It means less power is lost in a laser cavity and laser threshold is lower. The main benefit of high Al_2O_3 doping levels is therefore to enable high Ho^{3+} content while maintaining a high Al/Ho ratio which leads to shorter laser cavity and lower laser threshold.

The fluorescence lifetime increases with Al/Ho ratio, see Fig. 5, but also a strong effect of the absolute Al_2O_3 content can be seen. Manufacturing method has negligible effect on fluorescence lifetime value. The favorable influence of high Al_2O_3 concentration on Ho^{3+} fluorescence lifetime, thanks to its glass matrix modification and reduction of phonon energy, has already been discussed elsewhere [5], and similar results were obtained also in thulium-doped fibers [20].

In general, alumina has two basic effects; it prevents clustering of Ho^{3+} by creating non-bridging oxygens, and it lowers the phonon energy of the silica matrix [21,22]. Regarding SE and threshold, an Al/Ho ratio around 50 is the key factor. Further increase in the ratio gives only a minor effect. On the other hand, adding more alumina into the glass matrix (at the same Ho^{3+} concentration) further reduces the matrix phonon energy and thereby improves fluorescence lifetime.

To prove these assumptions and show the trends more clearly, we investigated the influence of absolute alumina concentration on the studied parameters, while the Al/Ho ratio remained nearly fixed. To do so, we selected 8 fibers with various Al_2O_3 concentration and similar Al/Ho ratio, and we compared their parameters. The fibers are listed in Table 2. They were prepared through various techniques, and some of the data were taken over from our previous publications [4,5].

Using fibers prepared through four different methods, we covered a range of roughly 2–9 mol.% of Al_2O_3 while keeping the Al/Ho ratio in a relatively narrow range around 25 ± 5 . Even though the ratio is quite far from the optimum one (Al/Ho = 50), and despite its variation, the trends presented below are quite clear. See Fig. 6 for slope efficiency versus Al_2O_3 concentration and Fig. 7 for fluorescence lifetime versus Al_2O_3 concentration.

Table 1
Relevant parameters of the fibers under study.

Sample	Al_2O_3 (mol.%)	Ho^{3+} (mol. ppm)	Al/Ho	SE (%)	Threshold (mW)	Fluorescence lifetime (μ s)	L_{opt} (m)	NA
NP_Al,Ho_1	7.38	5050	29	66.1	142	1200	0.4	0.240
NP_Al,Ho_2	6.85	6100	23	56.9	198	1040	0.4	0.230
NP_Al,Ho_3	6.31	7000	18	43.1	273	970	0.33	0.214
NP_Al,Ho_4	3.79	2850	27	65.1	238	1020	0.8	0.168
NP_Al,Ho_5	6.84	5350	26	60.6	180	1052	0.45	0.221
Powder_1	5.40	1450	75	79.9	127	1270	1.5	0.182
Powder_2	5.44	2300	47	70.7	125	1230	1	0.187
Powder_3	5.44	4050	27	63.4	142	1080	0.5	0.191

Fig. 2. Fluorescence decay properties of NP_Al,Ho_1 fiber a) decay curves for various excitation powers, b) decay time as a function of excitation power.

Fig. 3. Slope efficiency as a function of Al/Ho molar ratio.

Fig. 5. Fluorescence lifetime as a function of Al/Ho molar ratio.

Fig. 4. Laser threshold as a function of Al/Ho molar ratio.

25, the values range around 65% within the whole Al_2O_3 concentration region. The slightly lower value of fiber marked SD can be ascribed to lower value of Al/Ho ratio. Even though the SE is affected also by other parameters (such as background losses, which may show some variations) we can say, from the material point of view, the SE is intended primarily by Al/Ho ratio, rather than by Al_2O_3 concentration or preparation method.

In contrast with SE, the fluorescence lifetime increases linearly with Al_2O_3 concentration. This trend can be clearly understood considering the maximum phonon energy of silica glass is 1100 cm^{-1} while for aluminum oxide about 800 cm^{-1} is usually stated. Increasing Al_2O_3 content in silica thus reduces the matrix phonon energy, eliminates non-radiative transmissions and prolongs fluorescence lifetime.

4. Conclusions

We reported on a series of 8 silica-based holmium-doped fibers with various compositions prepared by powder-based method and MCVD in combination with nanoparticle doping. We studied fibers fluorescence and laser parameters in relation to their composition and preparation method. The obtained data on slope efficiency, laser threshold and fluorescence lifetime are in good agreement with previously obtained data on fibers prepared through different techniques. Thus, we conclude that the fluorescence and laser properties of fibers primarily depend on

The dependence of SE on Al_2O_3 is quite flat. For Al/Ho ratio roughly

Table 2
Selected fibers with similar Al/Ho ratio.

Sample	Al ₂ O ₃ (mol.%)	Ho ³⁺ (mol. ppm)	Al/Ho	SE (%)	Threshold (mW)	Fl. lifetime (μs)	L _{opt} (m)	Source
SD	2.80	2493	22	56.4	367	869	1.0	Ref. [4]
NP_low	2.90	1942	30	66.9	361	946	1.3	Ref. [4]
NP_Al,Ho_4	3.79	2850	27	65.1	238	1020	0.8	This work
Powder_3	5.44	4050	27	63.4	142	1080	0.5	This work
NP_Al,Ho_5	6.84	5350	26	60.6	180	1052	0.45	This work
NP_Al,Ho_1	7.38	5050	29	66.1	142	1200	0.4	This work
NP_high_1	8.80	6143	29	63.6	208	1190	0.5	Ref. [5]
NP_high_2	8.80	5705	31	70.3	156	1200	0.6	Ref. [5]

Note, the data taken over from Ref. [4] was treated according to the current methodology (already used in Ref. [5]) i.e. the average Al₂O₃ content was calculated only from 10 points around the flat-top center of the Al₂O₃ profile, not from all 20 measured points. Also, the Al/Ho ratio was based on Ho³⁺ concentration obtained from absorption measurements rather than using Ho³⁺ from EPMA. Based on our experience, this expression is more accurate and eliminates influence of possible dopant inhomogeneities.

Fig. 6. Slope efficiency versus Al₂O₃ concentration.

Fig. 7. Fluorescence lifetime versus Al₂O₃ concentration.

their chemical composition rather than on the preparation method.

We investigated the parameters as a function of Al/Ho molar ratio and total Al₂O₃ content. Laser slope efficiency is influenced primarily by Al/Ho ratio. Regardless of alumina concentration, the best slope efficiencies are obtained in fibers with molar ratio of Al/Ho greater than 50. The same value holds for the laser threshold. In this case, high Al₂O₃

doping enable high Ho³⁺ content while keeping sufficient Al/Ho ratio, which leads to shorter active fiber length and lower threshold values. Fluorescence lifetime increases with Al/Ho ratio as well as with the absolute Al₂O₃ concentration.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M. Kamrádek: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **R. Sajzew:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **J. Aubrecht:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **F. Lindner:** Investigation. **P. Vařák:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **O. Podrazký:** Investigation. **I. Bartoň:** Investigation. **J. Bierlich:** Investigation. **J. Dellith:** Investigation. **I. Kašík:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **K. Wondraczek:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **P. Peterka:** Funding acquisition. **P. Honzátko:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

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Data availability

The dataset supporting this study can be found in the following link, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18414762>

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